

Gender Responsiveness and Students' Academic Achievements in ICT in Education: The Role of Computer Game-Based Teaching Method.

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14841213

Abstract

The study examined the effects of computer games-based teaching method on gender responsiveness and students' achievements in Federal University Otuoke. While computer game-based teaching methods offer promising avenues for engaging students and promoting active learning experiences, questions arise regarding their differential impact on male and female students' achievements in the course, ICT in Education. Two research questions guided the study while three null hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance. The quasi-experimental design was adopted. A total of 340 300 Level students of ICT in Education in the Faculty of Education, made up the population of the study. The entire population of 340 students, was adopted since the population size was manageable. Therefore, there was no sampling. A 20-item validated ICT in Education Achievement Test (ICT-in-EAT) was used as the instrument for data collection. Three experts validated the instrument and an overall reliability index of .76 was obtained using Kuder-Richardson₂₀. Data related to the research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses. The findings from the study revealed that gender has a positive significant effect on male students' academic achievements when computer games-based teaching method was used in the teaching of ICT in Education. It was concluded that computer games-based teaching method is a gender responsive pedagogy. It was therefore, recommended that lecturers of ICT in Education should adopt and utilize the computer games-based teaching method as a teaching strategy more in male dominated classes since the approach favoured the male gender to attain higher academic achievements better than their female counterparts, among others.

Keywords: Computer, Game-based Approach, Gender, Achievements, ICT in Education.

Introduction

In recent years, the integration of technology into education has gained significant attention due to its potential to enhance teaching and learning experiences. One innovative approach that has emerged is the use of computer game-based teaching methods, which leverage the engaging and interactive nature of gaming to facilitate learning. This study explores the impact of such a teaching method on gender responsiveness and students' achievements in the context of ICT (Information and Communication Technology) education at the Federal University Otuoke.

Education in the view of the researcher and in the context of this paper, is the transfer of accumulated knowledge, norms and values of a given society, designed for the acquisition of one's cultural heritage, capable of molding one's behavior to be in tune with the civilized patterns of adulthood. It is therefore expected that in whatever form of education there is, an educated being

should live an acceptable lifestyle within the precepts of the society. These precepts are usually imbibed via the teaching and learning processes (Baral, 2023).

Learning is a process for creating knowledge and life experience to use it and apply it in real life situations (Steinkuehler, 2010). In traditional ways of teaching, ideas are presented in theoretical ways without sufficient opportunities for students to engage in classroom activities such as: problem solving, games playing, and laboratory experiments (Euler, 2011). Students have associated the feelings of success in school with fun because they feel motivated by it. At the same time, having fun in the process of learning varies, depending on the type of classroom activity they are engaged with (Sullivan, 1993 cited in Bragg, 2003), which extends to the undergraduate 300 Level class of ICT in Education

ICT (Information and Communication Technology) in Education refers to the integration and utilization of Information and Communication Technology tools, resources, and methodologies in the field of education. This specialized course combines principles from both education and technology to explore how digital tools can enhance teaching, learning, and educational management processes. ICT in Education plays a crucial role in modern education by enhancing teaching methods and student engagement. It enables diverse tools like interactive whiteboards, student devices for learning, and flipped classrooms (Western Australian Auditor-General, 2016). The impact of ICT on learning outcomes varies based on the educational program's design and implementation. The ICT for Education (ICT4E) framework focuses on sustainable pedagogical changes and cost evaluation (Rodriquez et al, 2012). By bridging the gap between biotic and abiotic entities in the education ecosystem, ICT can improve the teaching-learning process and address educational divides (Bandyopadhyay et al, 2021). Utilizing modern media and Microsoft tools, ICT enhances student motivation, interaction, and learning efficiency, requiring continuous teacher training (Delić-Zimić et al, 2017). ICT-enabled education promotes inclusive growth, literacy, and gender equity, bridging digital divides globally (Nair et al, 2013). Overall, ICT in education offers opportunities for innovation, collaboration, and enhanced learning experiences.

Teaching ICT in Education using computer games can enhance student engagement and learning outcomes. Educational computer games have been shown to positively impact students' attitudes towards subjects like mathematics (Husøy et al, 2020; Sahin et al, 2022). Incorporating digital games into teaching can provide new affordances in the classroom, offering students vicarious experiences and simulations. Additionally, ICT-enhanced tools like online applications and educational games can boost student exposure to course material, improving knowledge acquisition and skills development (Jamil et al, 2021). Educational games within professional development courses can help teachers develop practical ICT skills through experiential learning and mistake correction (Petelin et al, 2019). Therefore, integrating computer games into ICT education can be a valuable strategy for enhancing both students' and lecturers' ICT competences and engagements.

Computer games can indeed attract players' attention through immersive experiences, facilitated by cognitive flow and emotional engagement. The design of challenges, narrative elements, and player identity significantly contribute to sustained involvement and deep cognitive engagement in gameplay (Ojeda, 2007). The inclination of students to computer games has drawn significant attention. Researchers have found that using computer games to introduce new ideas can help teachers: build upon students' prior knowledge and skills, emphasize the connections among software concept information and its abstractions to real-world settings, as well as introducing more advanced ideas (Bransford, Brown, & Cocking, 2000). It helps students improve their

cognitive, social, and moral attitudes. It also helps students to be more creative and independent (Zavaleta, 2005). This strategy can build valuable student skills such as strategic thinking, planning, communication, negotiating skills, and data-handling (Kirriemuir & Mcfarlane, 2004). Computer games are 'activity-oriented' they involve challenges for students, have a set of rules to follow, have different choices, and have a set of cognitive objectives (Oldfield, 1992, cited in Ibtesam and Ahmed, 2014). To gain the greatest benefits of using computer games, teachers should do the following: encourage competition, target an important academic content, provide opportunities for students to examine their improvements and enjoy playing (Rideout, Foehr & Roberts, 2010). Computer game motivates students to spend time on tasks to master the required skills. The literature revealed that the educational games' design should include different elements, such as narrative context, rules, goals, rewards, and interactivity. Game design should have procedures to assess students' progress and feedback activities (Dondlinger, 2007). Using computer game as a software teaching method is considered as important tool in understanding new concepts, which makes it easier and could motivate one to learn (Akpinar, 2005). It is considered as interactive learning tasks for both school and the home. It also allows students to operate at different speed levels, as well as working independently (Davies, 1995, cited in Ibtesam and Ahmed, 2014).

The increasing prevalence of computer games among young male and female students has raised concern over its effects on gender responsiveness in the teaching and learning of ICT in Education towards attaining higher academic achievements.

The utilization of computer game-based teaching strategies in Computer studies has shown positive effects on students' retention abilities and gender responsiveness (Ngbarabara, 2023). Gender differences in the acceptance and impact of gamification techniques have been noted, emphasizing the need to consider gender when implementing such strategies. Educational computer games have been found to effectively enhance learning outcomes and motivation in both male and female students, providing an inspiring learning environment in secondary school computer science (Asmolov et al, 2023). To address the under-representation of girls in ICT, designing games that promote self-confidence, fight stereotypes, boost subject knowledge, and provide role models is crucial (Akre-Aas et al, 2022). Gamification, when tailored to combat gender inequality, can increase student engagement and inclusion in technology education (Theodoropoulos et al, 2022). By incorporating these insights into ICT in Education, higher academic achievements can be attained while promoting gender responsiveness.

Gender is a social construct that differentiates a man from a woman in a given society. Gender differences in achievement have been examined for some time resulting in a substantial body of literature (Jack & Johannes, 2001). The importance of examining instructional strategy in relation to gender is based primarily on the socio-cultural differences between girls and boys (Abra, 2000). Traditionally, girls in our society have been encouraged to conform, whereas boys are expected to be active and dominant risk-takers. Corroborating this view, Hassan and Ogunyemi (2008) acknowledges that most boys are provided with toys that enhance their visual-spatial ability such as trucks, Legos (toys consisting of plastic building blocks and other components) and models. Spencer (2004) also affirms that that the games of girls are often highly structured requiring turn taking and rules. Thus, social expectations and conformity pressures may create cultural blocks to girls in the use of computer games. Fabunmi (2004) in a study on gender composition has discovered a significant relationship with students' academic performance and that gender composition has a significant influence on secondary school students' academic performance.

Ezeudo and Ezinwanne (2013) discovered no significant difference in achievement of male and female students in Chemistry concepts. Studies on gender and academic achievement is therefore, inconclusive, while Azubuike (2015) discovered a significant gender difference in academic achievement in physical and health education when inquiry method is used, Obih (2017) discovered no significant gender difference in academic achievement of students in economics under the interactive influence of inquiry, cooperative and discovery methods. In other words, the influence of gender may vary depending on the subject or course, the instructional strategy used and the ability of the lecturer to teach the course.

Considering the increasing rate of addiction to computer games among young male and female Nigerian students, the present study investigated the effects of computer games-based teaching method on gender responsiveness and students' academic achievements in the teaching and learning of ICT in Education in Federal University Otuoke.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the growing recognition of the potential benefits of integrating technology into education through innovative teaching strategies, such as computer game-based teaching, there remains a need to understand its specific effects on gender responsiveness and students' achievements in the context of ICT in Education. This need is particularly pertinent within the academic environment of the Federal University Otuoke in Bayelsa State, where the dynamics of gender roles and academic achievements in ICT in Education warrants closer investigation.

While computer game-based teaching methods offer promising avenues for engaging students and promoting active learning experiences, questions arise regarding their differential impact on male and female students' achievements in the course, ICT in Education. The gender responsiveness of such teaching strategies, including how they cater to the learning needs and outcomes of male and female students, requires careful examination to inform inclusive educational practices.

Additionally, the academic setting of Federal University Otuoke presents a unique context shaped by regional, institutional, and cultural factors that may influence students' interactions with computer game-based teaching methods in the course of study. Understanding these contextual peculiarities is crucial for developing targeted solutions and pedagogical approaches that can address gender-related disparities and optimize learning outcomes for all students.

Consequently, this study addressed the specific effects of computer game-based teaching method on gender responsiveness and students' achievements in the course, ICT in Education at the Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. The study aims to provide evidence-based insights and recommendations that will contribute to the design of effective, gender-responsive pedagogical practices, tailored to meet the objectives of the university's undergraduate students in the Faculty of Education.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study was to determine the effects of computer games-based teaching method on gender responsiveness and academic achievements in ICT in Education at the Federal University Otuoke. Specifically, the study sought to determine the:

1. mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught ICT in Education with computer game-based teaching method (Experimental group) and those taught using expository teaching method (Control group).

2. mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught ICT in Education with computer games-based teaching method (Experimental group).

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught ICT in Education using computer game-based teaching method (Experimental group) and those taught using expository teaching method (Control group) in both pre-test and post-test?
2. What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught ICT in Education with computer game-based teaching method (Experimental group)?

Hypotheses

The following three hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance:

- HO₁:** There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught ICT in Education using computer game-based teaching method (Experimental group) and those taught using expository teaching method (Control group).
- HO₂:** There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught ICT in Education using computer game-based teaching method (Experimental group).
- HO₃:** There is no significant interaction effect of gender and methods (computer games-based teaching method) on students' achievements in ICT in Education.

Method

The study adopted the quasi-experimental research design. The study population consisted of 340 300 Level students of ICT in Education drawn from two intact classes of Science Education and Business & History Education programmes respectively, all from the Faculty of Education, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. The entire 340 population size was adopted as sample for the study since the population size was manageable. Using the census sampling technique, a total of 340 students were drawn from the three undergraduate programmes under the Faculty of Education, 156 students (89 males and 68 females) from the Department of Arts Education, 90 students (16 males and 74 females) from the Department of Business Education and 94 students (53 males and 41 females) from the Department of Science Education. This is because gender is a variable in the study. In each of the three programmes sampled, the intact classes of 300 Level students were used based on census sampling. The treatment group total (98 Males and 74 females = 172) while, the control group was (95 males and 73 females = 168), making up the total of 340 students used for the study. The instrument for data collection was a 20-item validated ICT in Education Achievement Test (ICT-in-EAT). The ICT-in-EAT was made up of twenty (20) multiple-choice questions drawn from general course outline of EDU 305 (ICT in Education). In constructing the Achievement Test, the researcher prepared the table of specification (Test Blueprint) based on the Benchmark for Minimum Academic Standards (BMAS) of undergraduate students' curriculum, to serve as a guide for the test development. Face validity of the instrument was established based on the inputs from the three experts who validated the instrument. To establish the internal consistency of the instrument, the Kuder-Richardson₂₀ formula was used to analyze the data using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 and obtained

a reliability index of .76. Data collected regarding the research questions were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) for the two research questions. The analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the three null hypotheses. The decision rule regarding the research questions was; reject the null (H_0) if the significance of F-Critical value is less than .05, otherwise, do not reject.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of students taught ICT in Education using computer games-based teaching method (Experimental group) and those taught using expository teaching method (Control group) in both pre-test and post-test?

Table 1: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviations of Students taught ICT in Education using Computer Games-Based Teaching Method (Experimental group) and those taught using the Expository Teaching Method (Control group) in both Pre-test and Post-test

Groups	Number	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)
Experimental Group	172	48.38	11.54	54.89	18.91
Control Group	168	41.11	10.39	48.69	15.33
Total	340				

Data on Table 1 showed that at pre-test, the achievement mean score for experimental group was 48.38 with a corresponding standard deviation of 11.54 respectively. After post-test, it was observed that for the experimental group, mean achievement score was 54.89 with a standard deviation of 18.91 respectively. For the control group, at pre-test, the achievement mean score was 41.11 with a corresponding standard deviation of 10.39 respectively. After post-test, it was observed that for the control group, mean achievement score was 48.69 with a standard deviation of 15.33 respectively.

This implies that students in the experimental group achieved higher than those in the control group considering their higher mean achievement scores at posttest. As a result of this observed difference in mean achievement scores, hypothesis 1 was tested at .05 level of probability to determine if these observed differences were significant.

Research Question 2: What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviations of male and female students taught ICT in Education using Computer Games-Based Teaching Method (Experimental group)?

Table 2: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviations of male and female students taught ICT in Education using Computer Games-Based Teaching Method (Experimental group)

Groups	Number	Pre-test	Post-test
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		Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (s)
Experimental (Male)	98	41.26	10.09	51.44	15.71
Experimental (Female)	74	37.56	9.41	43.66	12.03
Total	172				

Data on Table 2 showed that at pre-test, the achievement mean score for male students was 41.26 with a corresponding standard deviation of 10.09 and the female students mean score was 37.56 and a standard deviation of 9.41 respectively. After post-test, it was observed that the male students' mean achievement score was 51.44 with a standard deviation of 15.71 respectively. For the female students at pre-test, the achievement mean score was 43.66 with a corresponding standard deviation of 12.03 respectively.

This implies that the male students in the experimental group achieved higher than the female students in the same group considering their higher mean achievement scores at posttest. However, to determine if these observed differences were significant, hypothesis 2 was tested at .05 level of probability.

Hypotheses

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught ICT in Education using Computer Games-Based Teaching Method (Experimental group) and those taught using expository teaching method (Control group).

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on the mean achievement scores of students in experimental and control groups

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	181.34 ^a	1	181.34	9.43	.01	Rejected
Intercept	210032.0	1	210032.0	348.91	.00	
GROUP	174.31	1	174.31	9.43	.01	
Error	3209.01	337	21.02			
Total	203911.06	340				
Corrected Total	7633.08	339				

The table above showed the ANCOVA on the mean achievement scores of students in experimental and control groups. In table 3 above, the experimental and control groups as main effect, gave an F-value of 9.43 and was significant at .01. Since .01 was less than .05, this means that at .05 level of significant, the F-value was significant. Hence, hypothesis 1 was rejected. The findings revealed that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of

students taught ICT in Education using Computer Games-Based Teaching Method (Experimental group) and those taught using expository teaching method (Control group).

HO₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught ICT in Education using Computer Games-Based Teaching Method (Experimental group).

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on the mean achievement scores of male and female students in the experimental group

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	481.67	1	481.67	17.39	.00	
Intercept	8481.55	1	8481.55	376.14	.00	
GENDER	513.60	1	513.60	17.39	.00	Rejected
METHODS	151.42	1	151.42	6.50	.01	
Error	6871.33	337	25.66			
Total	148630.11	340				
Corrected Total	8048.10	339				

The above table showed the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on the mean achievement scores of male and female students in experimental group. In table 4 above, gender as main effect gave an F-value of 17.39 and was significant at .00. Since .00 is less than .05, this signifies that at .05 level of significant, the F-value was significant.

HO₃: There is no significant interaction effect of gender and method (computer games-based) on students' achievement in ICT in Education.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on the interaction between gender and computer games-based teaching method on students' achievement scores

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	189.59	1	189.59	7.43	.00	
Intercept	23407.44	1	23407.44	1045.76	.00	
METHOD*GENDER	197.43	1	197.43	7.43	.00	Rejected
Error	3761.44	337	20.54			
Total	106431.85	340				
Corrected Total	5688.55	339				

Table 5 above showed the interaction effect between gender and method on students' achievement in ICT in Education. The results indicated that the main interaction effect gave an F-value of 7.43 and this is significant at .00. Since .00 is less than .05, this means that at .05 level, the F-value of 7.43 is significant. Therefore, hypothesis 3 is rejected as stated, indicating that there was

significant interaction effect between gender and computer game on students' achievement in ICT in Education.

Discussion of Findings

Mean achievement scores of students taught ICT in Education using Computer Games-Based Teaching Method and those taught with the expository method

The finding revealed that computer games-based approach has positive effects on students' academic achievement in system software in secondary school than the expository approach. This implies that computer games-based approach can be used to improve students' academic achievement in ICT in Education. There are indications that students taught with computer games approach performed better after being exposed to the treatment. Implying that computer games approach is a good instructional method, and can be used to improve students' performance in ICT in Education.

In affirmation to this finding, Kim and Chang (2010) examined the effects of playing computer games on math achievement of 4th graders, with special focus on gender and language minority groups revealing that computer games improved or increased academic success and retention of students. Also, Fatokun, Egya and Uzoechi (2012), revealed that the computer games instructed students had higher scores in the post-test and delayed post-test, compared to those exposed to expository method of teaching. Similarly, Istifanus (2017) finding indicated that computer games teaching affects knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation. It was concluded that computer games can be helpful in improving students' academic achievement.

Further analysis revealed that there was a significant difference between the mean academic achievement score of students taught system software with computer games method and those taught with expository method. This is a clear indication showing that computer games approach has positive effects on students' academic achievement. Hence, this is confirmed by the study of Umeh, Nsofor, Oboh and Idris (2013) on Computer Game Assisted Instruction (CGAI) and Students' Achievement in Social Studies, which showed that there is a significant difference in the achievement of students in favour of CGAI.

Mean achievement scores of male and female students taught ICT in Education using Computer Games-Based Teaching Method

It was revealed in this study that male students achieved better than the female students taught ICT in Education using Computer Games-Based Teaching Method. This result is not surprising because male students have been noted to be conversant with computer games and to out-perform their female counterparts in any science related course. This implies that the male students benefited more when taught with computer games teaching method than the female students. This also implies that computer game-based teaching method enhances the academic achievement of male students more than the female students. Computer games-based teaching method therefore, concretizes learning to male students more than the female students.

Further findings revealed that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught ICT in Education using Computer Games-Based Teaching Method. The finding is in accordance with Sampath (2010) who reported that male students achieved higher than their female counterparts and the difference was significant at $P=.05$. This finding disagrees with Adigun, Onihunwa, Irunokhai, Sada and Adesina (2011) who studied effect of gender on students' academic performance in Computer Studies in Secondary Schools in New Bussa, Borgu Local Government of Niger State. The results of the study showed that even

though the male students had slightly better performance compared to the female students, it was not significant. The dissimilarities recorded in the finding could be attributed to the geographical area and nature of the studies.

Conclusion

The study revealed that computer game-based teaching method is an effective method in improving students' academic achievement especially in ICT in Education. The study revealed that students taught with computer game-based teaching method achieved higher mean academic achievement scores than those taught with expository method.

Therefore, computer game-based teaching method is an effective pedagogy in improving students' academic achievement for male and female students. Hence, a significant difference exists in male and female students' academic achievements in ICT in Education. The study, hereby, concluded that computer game-based teaching method should be introduced and replicated in other course in the faculty as it is a gender responsive pedagogy.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the findings of the study:

1. The University administration should provide enabling computer games-oriented instructional aid to all faculties, especially, the Faculty of Education.
2. Professionally qualified Computer Science Education experts should be assigned to teach ICT in Education as a course.
3. Teacher preparatory institutions should incorporate computer games teaching methods into the relevant areas of their curriculum units and expose both pre-service and in-service teachers to the use to enhance teaching and learning.
4. Male and female students should be equally exposed to computer games-based teaching approach since the study revealed that their activities are natural to students and is gender responsive.

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